

WOMEN AND GIRLS IN SCIENCE HAVE THE POWER TO CHANGE THE WORLD

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Abstract: *This article discusses the development of society as one of the most pressing issues in today's globalized world, which is directly related to the participation of young women with high scientific potential, the importance of the role of young women in science. Supporting their aspirations, strengthening the mechanism for the protection and implementation of their rights in this area, and the challenges facing the education of young women around the world are highlighted as much as possible. The author also mentions the work of the United Nations and UNESCO in support of women and the special programs adopted by women and girls to promote their education.*

Keywords: *Current issues of science, globalization, discrimination, society, UN, UNESCO, gender equality, inclusive education, special programs, exact sciences, science, scientific worldview, intellectual potential, STEM program.*

We mainly consider processes ranging from climate change to technological disruptions as major challenges of the 21st century. But the neglect of our women and girls in society, in the field of education, is also becoming one of the most pressing issues that need to be addressed today. This is also the case with ordinary learning. That is why the world should not be deprived of the potential, intelligence or creativity of thousands of our women and young girls who are victims of deep inequality and superstition. The situation of discrimination¹ against our young women and girls in education and science also has a direct negative impact on the development of society. Because education is a process aimed at expanding the opportunities for a person to make a competent choice of life path and self-development of the individual, it is a process and result of goal-setting, pedagogically organized and systematic socialization of the

¹ Discrimination (lot. discriminatio - differentiation) - restriction of the rights of the state, legal entity or individual (in relation to the rights of another state, legal entity or individual). Domestic laws of democracies and international law prohibit all forms of discrimination, including the practical or legal discrimination of citizens' rights on the basis of nationality, race, sex or religion.

person. Through education, a person creates an image of the world by taking an active position in the world of objective, social and spiritual culture. Education is also a mechanism for mastering culture. By expanding the education of our women and girls, we will also help them find their place in society as cultured individuals. Because education and culture are closely intertwined. A civilized person is an educated person. Education is the basic cultural form of human existence as it is teaching, educating, shaping. It is impossible to imagine human life without the realization of cultural patterns and human interactions with the world in the educational space. Education is not only a means of transmitting culture, but it also forms a new culture, develops society and leads to higher goals.

The activities of young women play an important role in the development of society. The need for pedagogical and communication technologies to ensure the active participation of women in all spheres of society and their interaction is becoming one of the most pressing issues in science today. That is, it is necessary to use pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the modernization of their activities. Today, in many countries around the world, women make up half of the population, but the percentage of participation in science is very low. I would like to emphasize that the task of creating a more just and inclusive world lies not only with women, but also with men, who must take responsibility and actively work to end discriminatory systems.

For example, more girls are in school today than ever before, but they do not always have the opportunity to complete and benefit from the education of their choice like boys. Many young girls and women are held back or hindered by misconceptions, social norms, and expectations that affect the quality of education they study and the sciences they study. They are particularly rare in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education and similar STEM² careers. To put an end to such negative situations, the United Nations General Assembly declared February 11, 2015 as the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, which calls for the full and equal use of science by women and girls. As well as gender equality and empowerment of women. Every year on February 11, International Women's Day is celebrated. One of the reasons for celebrating this day internationally is to encourage women and girls to participate fully and equally in science.

On December 22, 2015, the UN General Assembly resolution decided to mark International Day every year to recognize the important role of

² STEM - Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics

women and girls in science and technology. The International Day of Women and Girls in Science, celebrated on 11 February, is organized by UNESCO and UN-Women (link is external) through cooperation institutions and civil society partners to encourage women and girls in science. This day is an opportunity to encourage full and equal access and participation of women and girls in science. Gender equality is a global priority of UNESCO, and the ability to support young girls, educate them and fully express their ideas is a support for development and peace.

If we look at the statistics, women accounted for one in three surveyors (33%) in 2018. They have achieved equality in the sciences of life in many countries, and in some cases even dominate the field. However, they account for a quarter (28%) of graduates in engineering and 40% in computer science. Only 22 percent of AI³professionals are women. Surprisingly, these industries are leading the fourth industrial revolution. Women and girls still make up only 28 percent of engineering graduates and 40 percent of computer science graduates, according to experts from UNESCO's Department of Gender Science. Women are also a minority in technical and leadership roles in technology companies. In the United States, for example, the main reason women leave their jobs in the world of technology is a lack of appreciation. Such situations are a major obstacle to the development of science in society today.

According to UNESCO, less than one in four researchers in the business world are women, and women have difficulty accessing finance when they start their own businesses. In 2019, only 2% of capital in large sectors will go to women-based startups. There are countries that have taken steps to support women entrepreneurs. For example, in 2018, the Chilean government introduced the "Human Capital for Innovation in Women in Enterprises" scheme. She plans to co-finance up to 30 million pesos (about \$ 40,000) for technology-based startups founded by women.

Supporting the participation of women and young girls in science, focusing on their research, further strengthening the right to education is one of the pressing issues of today. Violation of their right to education can lead to gender inequality in society and exacerbation of current problems in science.

It is true that today women around the world have reached parity⁴ (45-55%). They continue their studies at the bachelor's and master's levels and at the PhD level (44%), but the gender gap tends to widen as they continue

³ Artificial intelligence

⁴ Parity lot.paritas means equality, equal rights, equal representation

their careers. To prevent this, we need to create as many opportunities for women and girls as possible to be educated. As a result, we will help our young girls and women to become educated, intellectually gifted, open-minded, independent-minded people and to have their own place in society.

Turning to the statistics again, in 2013, female researchers in 107 countries accounted for 28.4 percent, and in 2018, 33.3 percent of all researchers. In 2018, the share of female doctoral graduates worldwide was 44%, and the share of female researchers worldwide was 33%. In the same 2018, the share of women professionals was 22% worldwide. In 2019, 2% of the capital directed to start-ups was contributed by women. Analyzing nearly 3 million computer science articles published in the U.S. between 1970 and 2018, experts concluded that women remain a minority in digital information technology, computing, physics, math, and engineering, and that gender equality will not be achieved until 2100.

Gender equality is not only a human right, but gender equality in general is one of the building blocks of a peaceful, prosperous and stable world. Today, in education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics, UNESCO prioritizes STEM and science education for girls. According to a new UNESCO report, only 35% of STEM students in higher education worldwide are women and young girls, but there are differences in STEM subjects. For example, only 3% of female students in higher education choose information and communication technologies (ICT). This gender disparity is also a cause for concern, especially since STEM careers are often referred to as future jobs that promote innovation, social well-being, inclusive growth and sustainable development. To reduce gender disparities in STEM occupations, it is important to encourage girls and women to continue their STEM education and training. To do this, take into account the following:

- Giving girls and women the opportunity to take the next step in their future university or career by educating them more about science;
- Raising awareness of the relevance and importance of science in the daily lives of girls and women;
- The involvement and participation of women in STEMs needs to be further enhanced by reducing gender gaps by eliminating discrimination, misconceptions and stereotypes.

The attention paid to women and gender equality in Uzbekistan, the conditions created, and the normative and legal acts adopted to support women's education are also noteworthy.

Our President Sh.M. The following remarks by Mirziyoyev at the International Women's Day 2020 are noteworthy: "If we want to bring up future Khorezmians, Fergana people, Berunis, Bukhara people, Ulugbeks, Navoi people, first of all, we need to bring up healthy, well-educated and spiritual mothers".

The legal framework for the support of women and girls has been created in our country, and 30 normative documents have been adopted. Currently, the number of women studying in higher education institutions of the country has reached about 365 thousand, which is 47% of the total number of students. There is a single electronic system for coordinating postgraduate education (phd.mininnovation.uz) with 2,483 women engaged in research in postgraduate education. In 2021, the number of women with a PhD degree reached 707 and the number of women with a PhD degree reached 2,861.

In conclusion, if we want to bring up our youth and children as healthy and harmonious people, loyal to the Motherland, we must first of all open the way to science and career for women and young girls.

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